

Welcome to the EXA4MIND Newsletter

Who are we? We are a Horizon Europe project that aims to build an extreme data platform that brings together large scale data storage systems and powerful computing infrastructures by implementing novel automated data management and effective data staging.

In the middle of the journey

By Jan Martinovič, project coordinator

Dear reader,

We are **in the middle of the journey with our ambitious EXA4MIND project**. Our goal of building an Extreme Data Platform that combines data storage systems and powerful computing infrastructures is taking clearer shape. We have reached milestones that are helping us to move forward and make continuous progress.

Read the project coordinator's full editorial

EXA4MIND and European Data Spaces

Data is changing the way we produce, consume and live. This is why the European Union published the [European Data Strategy](#) to lead the way towards the creation of [Common European Data Spaces](#). The strategy aims to **boost innovation, competitiveness and sustainability by unlocking the potential of data** while ensuring privacy, security and trust.

The **EXA4MIND project** is a **natural partner in the development of these common data spaces**. One of its key objectives is to integrate automated and distributed high-performance data analytics applications (HPDA) with European Data Spaces.

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Scientific contributions

Valeo4Cast: A Modular Approach to End-to-End Forecasting

[Valeo.ai](#) team, a member of the EXA4MIND consortium and leader of the project's industrial application case, has developed a new autonomous driving method for predicting the future movements of nearby objects. It is called '**Valeo4Cast: A Modular Approach to End-to-End Forecasting**', and is part of the methods or solutions that have participated in the [AV2 2024 Unified Detection, Tracking, and Forecasting Challenge](#), organised by [Argoverse](#).

'Valeo4Cast: A Modular Approach to End-to-End Forecasting', is the **result of extensive and innovative research supported by EXA4MIND** that will serve, among many other applications, to develop, demonstrate and improve the industrial application case for EXA4MIND.

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Synergies and partnerships

DataNexus: introducing the EU cluster harnessing extreme data using advanced European technologies

As part of the Horizon Europe funding programme, seven pioneering projects have received funding to **address the challenges posed by extreme data generated by IoT, industrial, business, administration, environmental, scientific and societal sources**. These projects are pursuing innovative approaches that integrate cutting-edge technologies, including Artificial Intelligence (AI), Internet of Things (IoT), High-Performance Computing (HPC) and Edge/Fog/Cloud Computing. The **DataNexus cluster** is dedicated to fostering a vibrant community within the seven projects.

[Discover DataNexus](#)

A new synergy established among two projects to foster European contributions in standardisation for big data

StandICT.eu & EXA4MIND announce their collaboration with an introduction of Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) signed between the projects. Both projects share intentions to foster future standardisation in management, processing and – most importantly – **exchange and usage of huge datasets across Europe**. This MoU will help to consolidate and realise these intentions on both sides.

StandICT.eu is a European coordination action that fosters the participation of European experts in international ICT standardisation.

[Read the PR](#)

Participation in international events

The EXA4MIND project presented at the HPCSE 2024 conference

The High Performance Computing in Science and Engineering ([HPCSE](#)) conference was held from 20 to 23 May this year in the Beskydy Mountains, Czech Republic. Organised by the [IT4Innovations National Supercomputing Center](#), the event **attracted 85 experts from various fields**. Among the attendees were the partners from the EXA4MIND project, including the coordinator Jan Martinovič, and Pinar Karagöz from [Middle East Technical University in Turkey](#) was one of the invited plenary speakers at the HPCSE 2024 conference.

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EXA4MIND at the IEEE / CVF Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Conference (CVPR)

The [IEEE / CVF Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Conference](#) (CVPR) is the **foremost computer vision event of the year**. The 2024 edition was held from 17 to 21 June in Seattle WA, USA. EXA4MIND was part of the conference thanks to our consortium members from the [Czech Technical University in Prague](#), Antonín Vobecký and Josef Šivic.

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Look back at the world's oldest HPC conference

The first [ISC High Performance conference](#) took place in 1986. Since then, ISC has grown into the world's oldest and Europe's most important HPC conference. This year's conference theme was 'Reinventing HPC', **emphasizing the need for a new perspective on high-performance computing**. [IT4Innovations](#) was one of the conference exhibitors. It promoted its activities and international projects in which it is currently involved. One of the promoted projects was EXA4MIND, which IT4Innovations coordinates.

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EXA4MIND at iRODS UGM 2024

The 6th annual [iRODS User Group Meeting](#) was held from 28 to 31 May in Amsterdam. iRODS has been utilised across various scientific domains for storing and sharing research data. It was attended by 150 participants representing dozens of **academic, government and commercial institutions**. Among the attendees were also **partners from the EXA4MIND project**: Martin Golasowski from [IT4Innovations](#) and Mohamad Hayek from [Leibniz Supercomputing Centre](#).

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